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THE ROLE OF ROMANIAN PUBLIC INSTITUTIONS IN ENSURING EQUALITY OF OPPORTUNITY AND TREATMENT FOR VULNERABLE GROUPS

Abstract: *In every society there are certain vulnerable groups that face the risk of social exclusion. These groups often lack support, live in chronic poverty, and are unable to take advantage of opportunities or protect themselves against problems that may arise. We may refer to: abandoned children, people with disabilities, ethnic minorities, certain categories of sick people (e.g., individuals infected with HIV), the elderly, single-parent families, etc. In the doctrine, it is a well-known fact that the phenomenon of social exclusion can be combated with the help of social inclusion. The role of social security should not be overlooked. Provided by the state, this protection system is closely linked to the social inclusion of vulnerable groups. Notably, the concept extends beyond mere financial protection to include efforts to ensure equal access to opportunities and services for all members of society, including disadvantaged or marginalized groups. In this context, the scientific approach aims to identify and analyze the ways in which Romanian public institutions intervene to ensure equal opportunities and treatment for these vulnerable groups facing the risk of social exclusion, and unable them to cope with problems in all spheres of social life.*

Keywords: *principle of equal opportunities and treatment, social inclusion, vulnerable groups, public institutions, legislative documents, social policies, public-private partnership.*

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1. Introduction

In this article, we aim to present and explore the link between the principle of equal opportunities and treatment, social inclusion and vulnerable groups in the context of public administration in Romania, which are essential elements in ensuring social equity. In the two parts covering theoretical foundation, we have outlined a general and comprehensive framework governing the principle of equal opportunities and treatment, as well as the role of public institutions in promoting social inclusion and supporting vulnerable groups.

The first part of this article is dedicated to analyzing the theoretical foundations of the principle of equal opportunities and treatment, social inclusion and identification of vulnerable groups. We refer to the Romanian legislation in this field, providing a detailed understanding of the principles and concepts involved. We present various definitions and doctrinal perspectives, highlighting the importance of equal opportunities as a basis in any equitable society. We have also paid particular attention to the concept of social inclusion, highlighting its complexity and its relationship with social exclusion, as well as the dimensions and particularities of vulnerable groups in the Romanian legislative context. In order to facilitate the understanding of the typology of people in need of state support, we provide a table containing examples of relevant Romanian legislative documents, thus centralizing the specific terminology and definitions used for each category of disadvantaged, vulnerable, or marginalized groups.

In the second part of the paper, we analyze the role of public administration and its institutions in promoting social inclusion and ensuring equal opportunities and treatment for disadvantaged groups. We explore the measures and initiatives taken by the public administration, the importance of social security, the collaboration of public governance with other relevant actors, and the challenges encountered in this process. For each challenge mentioned, we have identified solutions aimed at improving the social well-being of disadvantaged citizens, and emphasizing the importance of a collaborative approach between the public and private sectors.

From our perspective, the topic addressed is one of significant interest and deserves a more extensive analysis, which has been provided in the following sections.

2. Theoretical foundations on the principle of equal opportunities and treatment, social inclusion and vulnerable groups

2.1. Legal aspects regarding the principle of equal opportunities and treatment in Romania

Equal opportunities and treatment are an ideal which has been promoted since the inception of legislation on fundamental human rights. As a main element of the principle of non-discrimination, this concept aims to eliminate criteria that could disadvantage certain groups of people (Nagy, 2022: 671).

The existing dysfunctions in modern society, at both collective and individual levels, require ongoing multidisciplinary evaluations. Regardless of the factors affecting the reality, it is crucial for every element of the democratic mechanism (either international, national, or European) to contribute in an active way. Thus, the principle of equality, with its multiple facets, plays a fundamental role in this process (Gentimir, 2015: 121).

According to a doctrinal opinion (Vieru, 2016: 114), the principle of equality derives from the general constitutional provision which establishes that all Romanian citizens, regardless of race, religion, sex, language, origin, political affiliation or opinion, are entitled to enjoy equally all rights guaranteed by the laws and the Romanian Constitution. Therefore, Romania's citizens have equal access to participate in economic, political, social and cultural life. The principle provides for equality in rights between women and men, as well as equality regarding nationality, ethnic or social origin, wealth, religion and political affiliation. This equality applies to all rights, regardless of the field of activity and the normative acts regulating them (Vieru, 2016: 116). The principle entails the equality of all citizens in the field of social security. Thus, no one can claim more rights to protection or be discriminated against in any form in the exercise of these rights.

We can conclude that equal opportunities and treatment have become a fundamental ideal for any society, ensuring equal access to rights and participation in all spheres of public and private life, thereby contributing to ensuring social equity.

2.2. National regulations and European norms on social inclusion and social exclusion: concept, process, and dimensions

In recent years, social policies in Romania have broadened the approach related to vulnerable or disadvantaged groups by introducing the concepts of *social exclusion* and *social inclusion*. The shift in perspective was moti-

vated by the desire to move beyond the limitations of the concept of poverty, which strictly focuses on the lack of financial resources. From a historical point of view, it should not be forgotten that these concepts initially made their presence felt in the European landscape, in the first part of the 1990s (Onica-Chipea, 2015: 26), and were later introduced in the field of Romanian social policy.

Social inclusion is a key word in this article. For a better understanding of this topic, we first need to explore the legal definition of this term. Pursuant to the Romanian social assistance legislation, “*the process of social inclusion represents a set of multidimensional measures and actions in the fields of social protection, employment, housing, education, health, information-communication, mobility, security, justice and culture, intended to combat social exclusion and ensure the active participation of people in all economic, social, cultural and political aspects of society*” (Article 6 [cc] of the Social Assistance Act).¹

The interpretation of the legal article emphasizes the idea that social inclusion is both a concept and a complex process aimed at ensuring the active involvement of all members of society in various aspects of life, including social, economic, cultural and political ones. There is a close relationship between the concepts of social inclusion and social exclusion, as evidenced in the legal definition of these terms provided in Law No. 292/2011; the Social Assistance Act specifies that *combating social exclusion is achieved through the promotion of social inclusion*,² which demonstrates the interdependence between the two terms. Therefore, social inclusion is a correlative term, serving as a “*response policy*” in situations that may lead to the social exclusion of an individual or a social group (Onica-Chipea, 2023: 88).

Although this article focuses on the phenomenon of social inclusion, we must also point out to certain particularities (i.e. dimensions) of social exclusion. The doctrine has synthesized this phenomenon into four essential dimensions: 1) *economic exclusion*, which results from income inequality and poor employment opportunities; 2) *exclusion from social services*, which reflects unequal access to education, health, housing, and social protection, with negative effects on the quality of life; 3) *political exclusion*, which arises from the unequal distribution of power and political opportunities, as well as from unequal access to justice and freedoms; and 4) *cultural exclusion*, which stems from differences in the recognition / respect of cultural norms and traditions. These dimensions are interconnected and can hinder progress in other areas of social life (Vremiş, Toartă, Rojco, Cheianu-Andrei, 2010: 20).

¹ Law No. 292/2011 on Social Assistance, *Official Gazette of Romania*, No. 905 of 20 December 2011.

² Here, the italics have been used for emphasis (by authors).

Combating social exclusion, promoting social justice and fundamental rights, including the right to equal treatment and non-discrimination, are the essential objectives of the European Union. In this regard, we may refer to a number of documents on this matter, such as: the Lisbon European Council documents, the Social Policy Agenda, Structural Funds, the Progress Program, the Open Method of Coordination, and others.

The Europe 2020 Strategy was adopted by the European Commission in 2010, with the stated aim of transforming the European Union into a “*smart, sustainable, and inclusive economy*” characterized by “*high levels of employment, productivity, and social cohesion*” (Europe 2020 Strategy, 2020).³ The European regulation tends to reduce the social exclusion of vulnerable groups to the concept of economic exclusion, generated by unforeseen socio-economic imbalances in the population, such as loss of employment, housing, physical capacity of the individual, which generate an income insufficiency that leads to monetary poverty. At the same time, European norms propose concrete intervention methods to reduce the risk of social exclusion for affected vulnerable groups, including the implementation of a minimum insertion income, a complex selective social assistance benefit, adequate wages and pensions, updating the Social Reference Indicator, and so on.

2.3. Vulnerable groups: definitions and terminologies in Romanian legislative documents

We begin this section by defining the concept of “*vulnerable groups*”. Although there are several officially proposed definitions, it is important to note that there is no clear consensus on the exact characteristics of groups which are considered to be “vulnerable”.

Consequently, vulnerable groups can be defined as “*undersupported groups who are often in a chronic state of poverty, unable to take advantage of opportunities or defend themselves against problems that may arise. Examples of this are disabled people, abandoned children, people infected with HIV, the elderly, ethnic minorities, single-parent families, etc. They represent a category that accumulates risks in all dimensions of life, unable to face difficulties.*” (Popescu, 2011: 10). The most common meaning of vulnerability is “*lack of means*”, “*weakness*”, “*lack of defense*”. The term “*vulnerable group*” is frequently encountered in official documents, legislation and/or research reports, being associated with expressions such as “*disadvantaged group*”, “*marginalized*”, “*excluded*” or “*risk group*” (Popescu, 2011: 9).

³ EUR-Lex (2020), *EUROPE 2020 A strategy for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth*, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52010DC2020>

Thus, the Romanian legislator approaches the notion of social exclusion in a broad sense; the approach is designed to encompass all dimensions of the phenomenon mentioned above, and uses different but identical or similar terms to define vulnerable groups. In order to illustrate the diversity of concepts in Romanian legislation, we have created a table which includes five examples of normative acts that use the term “vulnerable group” or another synonymous phrase, detailing their scope and outlining their broad content (Table 1). The table comprises three main columns: *Legislative document*, *Term used*, and *Definition/description*. The first column provides the name of the legislative document, the second column notes the specific term used in that document, and the third column provides the definition or description of that term. This comparative approach is aimed at understanding the differences and similarities between terms in different legislative contexts, and facilitating the interpretation and application of the legislation in force. It also provides an overview of the types of people who fall into this category.

Table 1. The concept “vulnerable groups” in Romanian legislation

Legislative document	Term used	Definition / description
Law No. 292/2011 on social assistance	Vulnerable groups	<i>“individuals or families who are at risk of losing the ability to meet their daily living needs due to illness, disability, poverty, drug or alcohol addiction or other situations leading to economic and social vulnerability.”</i> ⁴
Law No. 129/1998 on the establishment, organization and functioning of the Romanian Social Development Fund	Disadvantaged groups	women victims of domestic violence
		poor women
		poor pregnant teenagers
		poor parents with dependent children
		street children
		people who are homeless
		certain categories of sick people
poor elderly without family support		
Law No. 116/2002 on the prevention and combating social marginalization	Marginalized people	<i>“Social marginalization, in the sense of this law, is defined by the peripheral social position, isolation of individuals or groups with limited access to the economic, political, educational and communicational resources of the collective; it manifests itself through the absence of a minimum of social living conditions.”</i> ⁵

⁴ Article 6 [p] , Law No. 292/2011 on Social Assistance, *the Official Gazette of Romania*, No. 905, 20th Dec. 2011.

⁵ Article 3, Law no. 116/2002 regarding the Prevention and Combating of Social Marginalization, *the Official Gazette of Romania*, No. 193, 21st March 2002.

GEO No 68/2003 on social services	Social groups, individuals and families in difficulty or at risk, generating marginalization or social exclusion	people addicted to alcohol or other intoxicating substances
		people who left prisons
		single parents
		victims of human trafficking
		people with no or low income
		immigrants
		people infected or sick with HIV/AIDS
		chronically ill or suffering from incurable diseases
		homeless people
		elderly people
		children
Joint Memorandum on Social Inclusion, MMFPS, 2005, section 2.6	Vulnerable groups	homeless people
		child at high-risk situations
		young people over the age of 18 who are no longer in the care system for children/youth without families
		elderly people at risk
		Roma people at risk
		people with disabilities

Source: Table prepared by authors, based on data collected from the referenced legislation

The role of public administration and its institutions in promoting social inclusion and ensuring equality of opportunity and treatment for vulnerable groups

3.1. Public administration and equal opportunities: measures and initiatives for social inclusion

Even though today's society has made progress, it is still not perfectly fair and just from a social point of view. Persistent differences between social groups can create inequalities in access to resources and opportunities for success. A truly inclusive society should give every person the possibility to fully realize their potential, regardless of their background or circumstances. Within the administrative space, one can still observe the manifestations of inequity and social exclusion. However, it is believed that transparency and participation in the exercise of public authority can correct the discrepancies with the standards of social justice (Juridice, 2023). In this context, we can mention the important role that *social security* plays in a social and legal system.

According to the definition given by the International Labor Office, *social security* refers to the protection offered by society to its members through various public measures. This kind of measure is intended to prevent social and economic difficulties caused by loss or significant reduction in income for reasons such as sickness, maternity, labor accidents, unemployment, disability, old age, or death. Social security also encompasses healthcare provisions and allowances for families with children (Vieru, 2016: 110).

Some authors consider that social security is a guarantee against various types of risks, such as: *psychological risks* (including illness, disability, death, maternity, old age); *social risks* which may affect individuals, resulting in a reduction or loss of earnings; and *occupational risks*, such as occupational diseases and accidents at work (Țiclea & Georgescu, 2021: 6).

From our point of view, social security is closely linked to the social inclusion of vulnerable groups because an important part of social security is to ensure that all members of society, including the vulnerable groups, have access to a minimum level of well-being and protection against social exclusion, as well as equal opportunities and equal treatment. Thus, the concept of social security extends beyond mere financial protection and includes efforts to guarantee equal access to opportunities and services for all society members, including vulnerable or marginalized groups.

Based on a brief analysis of doctrine in the field of social security and welfare, we may list several examples illustrating the role of public administration and its institutions in promoting social inclusion by ensuring the application of the principle of equal opportunities and treatment:

- Developing legislation and policies for social inclusion;
- Monitoring and evaluating the implemented social inclusion policies;
- Facilitating access to basic services, such as education, healthcare, housing, and social services, for all community members, including those considered vulnerable;
- Promoting labor market inclusion by employing and integrating people from vulnerable groups, offering vocational training programs, internships or facilitating access to jobs;
- Promoting diversity and inclusion in the community, through awareness campaigns, cultural events, or programs that promote diversity and combat discrimination/marginalization;
- Strengthening partnerships with NGOs and other national/international entities;

- Promoting dialog with citizens; it is important for the public governance to involve the community in the decision-making process and seek citizens' opinions in order to identify real needs and develop effective solutions for social inclusion.

These examples reflect various aspects of the addressed topic and emphasize the importance of public administration in promoting social inclusion and equal opportunities and treatment with direct applicability to vulnerable groups in society.

3.2. Collaboration between Public Administration and other relevant actors

In order to achieve the desired results particularly in terms of its role to promote social inclusion by applying the principle of equality of opportunity and treatment, public administration cannot operate in isolation, as a single entity, but must collaborate with other sectors, such as the private and the non-profit sectors, in order to create partnerships and solve complex problems (Iordache, 2023: 152). Addressing the social needs of different vulnerable groups in an integrated system is actually part of the same course of action: to ensure collaboration between all relevant actors in order to resolve the complex problems which are faced by these vulnerable groups at risk of marginalization and social exclusion.

In that context, it is essential to identify relevant actors that can work with the public administration to facilitate administrative processes mainly related to the social inclusion of vulnerable groups in a society, cover possible needs or shortcomings that the public administration cannot address alone, and ensure respect for the principle of equal opportunities and equal treatment. The doctrinal analysis highlights viable examples of relevant social actors who may collaborate with the administrative structures, some of which are:

- 1. NGOs**, such as associations and foundations which have an important role in social assistance in general and protection of vulnerable groups in particular, through sponsorships, donations, partnerships, concluded in compliance with the legal rules in force;⁶ associations and foundations also carry out economic activities through commercial entities using the income or profit for social or public benefit;
- 2. Voluntary organizations** providing services for vulnerable or at-risk groups; they collaborate with other entities (e.g. religious institutions, associations or economic agents) but operate independantly, relying on

⁶ See: Law no. 7/2024 for the approval of GEO no. 39/2018 on public-private partnership, the *Official Gazette of Romania*, No. 427, 18th May 2018;

their own income obtained through donor support;

3. **Individual and family enterprises** involved in activities aimed at promoting social inclusion (such as counseling, training, retraining or further training), with the ultimate goal of integrating vulnerable groups into society; they also focus on promoting economic activities that provide support to people in need, including manufacturing and marketing of products and services;
4. **Higher education institutions** which can contribute through various research or educational programs aimed at promoting community development and social inclusion;
5. **International government agencies or international organizations** which can support social inclusion programs;
6. **National or international private companies** which offer donations, sponsorships, grants (etc.) for the development of social environment;
7. **Cooperative societies** which use their profits for social purposes, while focusing on attracting external sources through projects and obtaining donations from cooperative members or external donors, either legal or natural persons (Ministerul Muncii, Familiei și Protecției Sociale, 2010).

3.3. Improving social inclusion and equal opportunities: challenges and solutions for Romanian public institutions

In the light of contemporary realities, public administration faces a series of complex challenges as democratic developments impose new standards which public administration has to adapt to. We must also take into account the fact that public organizations are becoming increasingly complex and hybrid as they attempt to address numerous and sometimes conflicting ideas, considerations, demands and cultural elements. As stated in the doctrine, one reason for this phenomenon is the fact that modern representative democracies institutionalize administrative policies and implement different generations of public sector reforms at an increasingly accelerated pace (Christensen, Læg Reid, 2011: 407).

In order to better understand the challenges faced by the Romanian government in applying the principle of equal opportunities and treatment, and ensuring the social inclusion of vulnerable groups, we may draw attention to following issues:

- bureaucracy and inefficiency in administrative processes;
- the need to develop and implement policies and programs tailored to

the specific needs of different social groups;

- limited resources and insufficient funding for social inclusion projects;
- lack of community awareness and involvement in efforts to promote social inclusion;
- lack of coordination and communication between various government agencies and non-governmental organizations involved in social inclusion initiatives;
- cultural and linguistic diversity, which requires adapting and customizing services to be accessible and relevant to different communities;
- deficient social infrastructure which must provide support for the inclusion of all citizens;
- marginalization and discrimination that can exist in society, making it difficult for certain groups to fully integrate and participate in social and economic life.

In terms of solutions for addressing the challenges presented above, we may mention some examples that we consider worthy to be taken into consideration:

- simplifying administrative procedures and reducing bureaucracy to improve efficiency and access to public services;
- direct consultation with vulnerable groups to understand their needs and develop customized policies that respond to their specific problems;
- searching for public-private partnerships and accessing European funds;
- creating awareness and education campaigns to engage communities in inclusion efforts, providing them with information on the importance and benefits of social inclusion;
- implementing collaboration and communication platforms to facilitate the exchange of information between the administration and the different entities involved;
- developing and delivering programs/services that are sensitive to cultural and linguistic diversity by involving community members in the design and implementation process;
- investments in social infrastructure to ensure equitable access to basic services (education, health, housing, etc.);

- promoting diversity and inclusion through education and awareness programs.

4. Conclusion

On the basis of the provided analysis, we can say that public institutions in Romania bear a great responsibility in terms of ensuring equal opportunities and equal treatment for vulnerable groups, which are at risk of social exclusion. Thus, the role of Romanian public institutions in ensuring equal opportunities and treatment for vulnerable groups is essential in combating social exclusion and promoting social inclusion. The public administration contributes to the creation of an equitable society by implementing and monitoring the relevant legislation, facilitating access to basic services, promoting diversity and inclusion in the labor market, as well as through partnerships with NGOs and other relevant social actors. In doing so, these institutions are committed to going beyond mere financial protection measures, ensuring equal access to opportunities, benefits and services for all members of society, and strengthening social security and thus reducing persistent inequalities.

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**УЛОГА РУМУНСКИХ ЈАВНИХ ИНСТИТУЦИЈА У ОБЕЗБЕЂИВАЊУ
ЈЕДНАКИХ МОГУЋНОСТИ И ТРЕТМАНА ПРИПАДНИЦИМА РАЊИВИХ
ГРУПА**

Резиме

Овај чланак представља општи и свеобухватан оквир о принципу једнаких могућности и третмана, као и о улози јавних институција у промовисању социјалне инклузије и подршци рањивим групама. Рад се фокусира на теоријске основе принципа једнаких могућности и третмана, социјалне укључености и идентификације рањивих група. Позива се на румунско законодавство у социјалној области, пружајући детаљно разумевање укључених принципа и концепата. Стога су представљене различите дефиниције и доктринарне перспективе, наглашавајући важност једнаких могућности као основе у сваком праведном друштву. Посебна пажња је такође посвећена концепту социјалне укључености, наглашавајући његову сложеност и однос са социјалном искљученошћу, као и димензије и посебности рањивих група у румунском законодавном контексту. На крају чланка, текст истражује примере мера и иницијатива које је предузела јавна управа, значај социјалне сигурности, сарадњу јавне управе са другим релевантним актерима и изазове са којима се сусреће у овом процесу, али и идентификовање решења која имају за циљ да побољшање друштвеног благостања појединаца у неповољном положају, наглашавајући важност заједничког приступа између јавног и приватног сектора.

Кључне речи: принцип једнаких могућности и третмана, социјална инклузија, рањиве групе, јавне установе, законодавни документи, социјалне политике, јавно-приватно партнерство.